

Systematic Evaluation and Usability Analysis of Formal Tools for System Design

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Abstract—Formal methods and supporting tools have a long record of successes in the development of safety-critical systems. However, it cannot be said that a single tool has emerged as the dominant solution for system design. Each tool differs from the others in terms of modelling language used, verification capabilities and other complementary features, and each development context has peculiar needs that require different tools. This is particularly problematic for the railway industry, in which formal methods are highly recommended by the norms, but no actual guidance is provided for the selection of tools. To guide companies in the selection of the most appropriate formal tools to adopt for their contexts, a clear assessment of the features of the available tools is required. To address this goal, this paper considers a set of 14 formal tools for system design, and presents a systematic evaluation of the tools and a usability analysis with practitioners. Results are discussed considering the most desired aspects by industry and previous related work. The focus is on the railway domain, but the overall methodology can be applied to similar contexts. Our study contributes with a systematic evaluation of formal tools and shows that despite the poor graphical interfaces, *usability* and *maturity* of the tools are not major problems, as claimed by other works. Instead, *process integration support* is the most relevant pain point for the majority of the platforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of railway safety-critical systems, such as platforms for on-board automatic train control [1], [2] or computer-based interlocking infrastructures to route the trains [3], [4], has to follow strict process guidelines to deliver products that are highly dependable and trustworthy [5], [6]. Formal methods are mathematically based techniques for the specification, analysis and verification of systems [7], and are particularly indicated when rigour is a main concern. They have a long history of over 30 years of success stories in railway applications [5], [8], [9], with several support tools available in the market [10]–[13]. Furthermore, the CENELEC EN 50128 norm [14], which is the standard for the development of railway software in Europe, highly recommends the usage of formal methods for design and verification of those products that need to meet the highest safety integrity levels.

Despite these premises, the adoption of formal techniques and their supporting tools by companies is still rather limited [15], [16], and railway practitioners ask for more guidance to select the most adequate formal tool, or set of tools, for their development contexts [17]–[19]. Previous work on applications of formal methods to railway problems has mostly focused on reporting experiences [1]–[4], [20]–[41]. Notable cases are the usage of the B method for developing the Line

14 of the Paris Métro and the driverless Paris–Roissy Airport shuttle [20], the use of Simulink for formal model-based development of the metro control system of Rio de Janeiro [2], and the application of NuSMV to the ERTMS/ETCS European standard for railway control and management [1]. Recently, a stream of literature emerged on the evaluation and comparison of formal tools in railway. Mazzanti et al. [42] replicates the same railway design with different tools, informally describing their peculiarities. Haxthausen et al. [43] compares two methods for the verification of an interlocking system. A recent work by Ferrari et al. [17] makes a step forward and performs a judgment study involving experts to provide a qualitative analysis of multiple formal tools, and, together with other authors [10], [19], recommends for more fine-grained and objective evaluations to guide practitioners in tool selection and answer the question “Does the tool fit my problem?” [18].

This paper extends the literature by performing a systematic evaluation of 14 formal tools for railway system design. To this end, we adapt the DESMET methodology for tool evaluation proposed by Kitchenham et al. [44]. We first select a comprehensive set of evaluation features based on a brainstorming involving formal methods and railway experts. Then, three assessors evaluate the tools and assign values to the features. To this end, they access the documentation, run the tools and perform trials to have an informed judgment. Multiple iterations and triangulation sessions are performed to ensure homogeneity in the assessment. As usability of the tools is considered as particularly relevant by railway practitioners according to recent surveys [45], [46], a usability study is carried out involving subjects from a company. The data of our study are shared to facilitate inspection and replication [47].

Our work gives the following main contributions: i) we provide a set of features to systematically evaluate formal tools for railways, which can be adapted to other domains; ii) we assess the features on 14 different tools and share the tool evaluation sheets; iii) we perform a comparative usability study of formal tools involving practitioners; iv) we debunk some common beliefs about formal tools, especially concerning usability and maturity.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Sect. II discusses background and related work. In Sect. III we illustrate the study design and in Sect. IV we report the results. Sect. V discusses implications. Sect. VI reports threats to validity and Sect. VII gives final remarks.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Formal Methods and Tools

Formal methods are mathematics-based techniques useful for the specification, analysis and verification of systems [7]. These methods are normally oriented to the development of mission-critical software and hardware, and are supported by software tools that can be used to model the system, perform automated verification, and, in some cases, produce source code and tests. The different formal techniques and tools that we consider can be partitioned into four broad families, namely *theorem proving* [48]–[50], *model checking* [51]–[53], *refinement checking* [54] and *formal model-based development* [22]¹. Here, we briefly discuss the main characteristics of the different families and point to representative tools.

Theorem proving applies the Curry-Howard correspondence between computer programs and mathematical proofs [55] to formally verify that some property holds in a system specification, by means of semi-automated proofs that require interaction with the user. Roughly speaking, a theorem prover helps the user in demonstrating theorems over a system specification. The theorems can be related to some invariant that must hold in the specification, or to the consistency of some specification refinement. Well-known theorem provers are Atelier B [56], Coq [48], and Isabelle [57].

Model checking [53], is a Turing awarded technique to verify that some desired property expressed with a declarative formalisation, normally a logic dialect, is satisfied by a specification. It is common to distinguish between linear time and branching time model checking, depending on the type of logic supported by the verification engine, and therefore the way in which the desired properties can be expressed. The success of this technique is mainly due to its full automation. Traditionally, the model checking problem is solved by generating and visiting the whole state space of the specification, composed with the property to be analysed. This is the approach of tools such as SPIN [58], UMC [59] and ProB [21].

The full state exploration leads to the well-known state-explosion problem, and several techniques have been developed to overcome this scalability issue, as for example symbolic model checking [60], supported by NuSMV/nuXmv [61], statistical model checking [52], [62], applied by UPPAAL [63], and automata minimization techniques, which are supported by CADP [9] and mCRL2 [32], two tools based on the formalism of process algebras.

Other tools, such as TLA+ [64] and SAL [65], take a different approach and combine model checking and theorem proving. Theorem proving does not depend on the problem space, and this avoids the state-explosion problem, although at the cost of a reduced automation.

Refinement checking [54] is a different verification technique that consists in automatically assessing that a certain specification is a correct refinement of a higher-level specification. This

¹As our focus is on system *design*, we do not consider deductive verification and abstract interpretation, which are applied to source code.

is the main technique used by FDR4 [54], but it is supported also by other tools, such as ProB [21].

Formal model-based development tools focus on specification through graphical models, which can be then simulated, analysed and verified by means of different techniques. Although these tools often embed model-checking capabilities to support verification, their main emphasis is in the modelling phase, and for this reason we classify them in a different family. Examples of these tools are Simulink [66], SCADE [67], Modelica [68] and also tools for Petri Nets [40].

The different families of formal tools briefly listed above give an intuition of the wide landscape of choice available. On the other hand, empirical comparisons between tools, both for railways and other fields, are limited [17]–[19]. This, together with other issues largely discussed in the literature, such as the prototypical level of the tools, the skills required, the psychological barriers, etc. [8], [15] has seriously hampered the adoption of formal tools by industrial practitioners. As observed by Steffen [19], “Prospective users have a hard time to orient themselves in the current tool landscape, and even experts typically only have very partial knowledge. Thus, the need for a more systematic approach to establish the profiles of tools and methods is obvious”. To address this issue, several efforts have been performed in the community of formal methods for system and software engineering. Well known initiatives targeting a more comprehensive and comparable view of formal tools are: tool competitions (see, e.g., [69], [70]), mostly oriented to assess performance over shared benchmarks [10]; the ETI initiative [71], aimed at creating an online service to experiment with different formal tools; the comprehensive study by Garavel and Graf [9], a report of over 300 pages characterising the landscape of available methods.

B. Formal Tools in Railways

The railway domain is characterised by a strong safety culture, supported by rigorous development practices oriented to prevent catastrophic system failures and consequent accidents. The CENELEC EN 50128 standard for the development of software for railway control and protection systems [14] considers formal methods as highly recommended practices when developing platforms of the highest Safety Integrity Levels (SIL-3/4). Given these premises, the railway domain has been a traditional playground for practical experimentation with formal methods [5], [8].

Formal modeling and verification tools commonly used in the railway domain have been reviewed in the past (cf., e.g., [5], [20], [72]–[75]). Bjørner [72] presents a first, non-systematic survey of formal methods applied to railway software. With a focus on the B method, the book edited by Boulanger and Abrial [75] discusses successful industrial usages, including railway experiences at Siemens and other companies. Aspects of railway system development are covered by the book edited by Flammini [74], where two entire chapters are dedicated to formal methods applications. New applications and future challenges related to the increasing complexity of railway systems are indicated in the reviews of

Fantechi *et al.* [5], [73]. A systematic literature review [11], including 114 research papers on formal methods and railways, and two surveys with practitioners [45], [46], were also recently published, highlighting the importance given by the railway industry to *maturity* and *usability* of formal tools.

Efforts in comparing formal tools have been performed also in railways. Specifically, Haxthausen *et al.* [43] compares two formal methodologies for interlocking system development. Mazzanti *et al.* [42] replicates the same railway design with multiple formal methods, and qualitatively discusses the peculiarities of each tool. During the ABZ 2018 conference, a case study track was specifically dedicated to a railway problem [76]. The specification provided by the organisers was modelled by different authors through different tools, including SPIN and ProB, leading to independent publications (e.g., [31], [38]). Ferrari *et al.* [17] performs a judgment study considering 9 tools, and produces a table with strengths and weaknesses, to guide the adoption of formal methods in railways. The study does not consider specific evaluation features, but takes a more bird-eye view on the tools.

Overall, none of the existing studies and initiatives, both in railways and in the other domains, performs a *systematic* evaluation of formal tools. The current work addresses this research gap. Compared to previous contributions in railways [17], [42], [43], [76], our work: 1) is systematic and considers a comprehensive set of evaluation features; 2) takes into account a larger set of tools; and 3) it is the first one presenting a usability study with practitioners.

III. RESEARCH DESIGN

Our study is oriented to provide a *descriptive* theory of the characteristics of available formal tools for railway system design, and achieve a more structured understanding of the field. To this end, we perform a systematic tool evaluation adapting the guidelines of the DESMET methodology by Kitchenham [44], according to the qualitative feature analysis paradigm. Specifically, we first select a set of relevant features, and then we consider existing documentation and perform tool trials to qualitative evaluate the features with a sufficient degree of objectivity. Usability in terms of ease-of-use is evaluated through a usability study. The produced comparison table and the results of the usability study are used as a basis to compare the different tools and discuss research gaps as well as mismatches between railway designers' expectations as identified by previous work [45], [46], and tools' functionalities and qualities. Although the DESMET methodology normally suggests a numerical scoring scheme for the evaluation features (i.e., qualitative values are mapped to numbers), we did not adopt this approach, as our goal is not to rank the tools, but to provide a comprehensive comparison without the need to establish winners and losers.

Our research focuses on the railway domain, given the long history of applications of formal methods in this field, and the demand for a more widespread knowledge dissemination towards practitioners and system designers [17], [18].

A. Research Questions

Our overall research goal is to systematically evaluate formal tools for system design in the railway domain. The goal is decomposed into the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: *Which are the features that should be considered to evaluate a formal tool?* This question aims at creating a taxonomy of features to evaluate the tools. To address this goal, we perform a brainstorming session of feature elicitation, followed by consolidation activities to come to a well defined set of features and associated values.
- RQ2: *How do different tools compare with respect to the different features?* With this question, we want to highlight strengths and weaknesses of the tools according to the selected features. The 14 tools are individually evaluated by three assessors with the support of the tools' documentation, research papers, and through brief trials with simple draft models defined by the assessors themselves. The evaluation enables the identification of individual as well as collective weaknesses and strengths of the tools. For each tool, an evaluation sheet is produced.
- RQ3: *How do different tools compare with respect to usability?* Usability is a particularly relevant macro-feature that needs to be assessed by different subjects to be properly evaluated. To compare the ease-of-use of the tools we perform a usability assessment with railway practitioners, and compute the usability of the tools with the System Usability Score (SUS) test.

B. Tools

The 14 selected tools for the evaluation are CADP (2020-g), FDR4 (4.2.7), NuSMV (1.1.1), ProB (1.9.3), AtelieB (4.5.1), Simulink (R2020a), SPIN (6.4.9), UMC (4.8), UPPAAL (4.1.4), SCADE (6), mCLR2 (202006.0), SAL (3.3), TLA+ (2) and CPN Tools (4.0). The first ten were included as they are evaluated among the most mature formal tools for railways, according to Ferrari *et al.* [17]. The last four were added to consider a more representative set of the different flavours of formal system modelling and verification available. Specifically, CPN Tools was included to consider Petri Nets, a widely used graphical formalism also for railway modelling [40], [46]. mCLR2 is based on the algebra of communicating processes and support minimization techniques, like CADP, but it is open source [32]. Finally, SAL and TLA+ are peculiar tools that integrate both theorem proving and model checking. TLA+ is also used at Amazon [77]. More information about the peculiarities of each tool is reported in the evaluation sheets that were produced for each tool [47]. Further work can update the list of tools, using the features proposed in this paper as reference for assessment. The tools were tried in their free or academic license, depending on the available options. The commercial license was not purchased for any of the tool.

C. Study Participants

Three main participants were involved in all the phases of the study and are referred as *assessors*. The assessors have from 3 to 12 years experience in formal methods applications to railways in both academic and industrial settings, and one of them has over 25 years of experience in formal methods, as well as hands-on experience on formal tool development.

Additional participants are: 3 researchers with more than 20 years of experience in formal methods applications to railways (referred as *academic experts*); 9 practitioners with more than 10 years of experience in railways, but no previous experience in formal methods applications (*industry experts*).

D. RQ1: Feature Selection

The features were elicited with a collaborative approach inspired by the KJ method [78]. A 3-hours workshop was organised involving 8 participants: the assessors, the academic experts and two of the industry experts. Participants were given five minutes to think about relevant features that should be considered when evaluating a formal tool for railway system design. Each participant wrote the features that they considered relevant in a sheet of paper that was not made visible to the others. Then, the moderator asked the participants to list their features and briefly discuss them. When the explanation given by the feature proponent was not clear, the others could ask additional questions to clarify the meaning of the feature. The moderator reported each feature in a list that was made visible to all participants through a projector. When a feature was already mentioned, it was not added to the list. At the end of the meeting, the assessors homogenised the feature names. For each feature, the assessors jointly defined the possible values, as well as a systematic way to assess it. The final list of features and possible values was later cross-checked by the other participants. A reference evaluation document was redacted with all the information to be included for each tool.

E. RQ2: Feature Evaluation

The three assessors performed the systematic feature evaluation. The assessors worked independently on a subset of the considered tools, and they produced an evaluation sheet for each tool, based on the reference document. The assessors worked on the tools that they were more familiar with, according to their previous experiences, so to give a more informed judgment. Specifically, one assessor used UPPAAL and Atelier B; one used Simulink and SCADE; the assessor with more experience in formal methods used the remaining tools. To perform the evaluation, the assessors followed a structured procedure: 1) install and run the tool; 2) consult the website of the tool, to check the official documentation; 3) opportunistically search for additional documentation to identify useful information to fill the evaluation sheet; 4) refer to the structured list of papers on formal methods and railways published in the previously referred literature review [11]² (see

²The list of 114 papers, and associated categories, was accessed at <https://goo.gl/TqGQx5>.

Sect. II-B), to check for tools' applications in railways; 5) perform some trials with the tools to confirm claims reported in the documentation, and assign the value to those features that required some hands-on activity to be evaluated; 6) report the evaluation on the sheet, together with the links to the consulted documents and papers, and appropriate notes when the motivation of some assignment needed clarification.

In subsequent face-to-face meetings, the assessors challenged each others' choices, and asked to provide motivations and evidence for the assigned values. The evaluation sheets were revised a second time by all the three assessors to align visions, and balance judgments. A summary table was produced to systematically compare the tools.

F. RQ3: Usability Evaluation

This section outlines the methodology adopted for the usability evaluation of the tools performed by railway experts. First, a set of models of the same sample system was developed by the assessors using 8 different tools, namely Atelier B, NuSMV, ProB, Simulink, SPIN, UMC, UPPAAL, and SCADE. The other tools were not included as, from the feature evaluation, they were considered to require *advanced* mathematical background to be understood (i.e., CADP, FDR4, mCLR2, SAL, TLA+, see Fig. 1), or were known from the literature to be inadequate to handle industry-size problems (this is the case of CPN Tools [42]). One exception is Atelier B, which, although requiring advanced background, is one of the few tools already used in the development of real-world railway products (see "Integration into the CENELEC process", Fig. 1).

Each assessor worked only on a subset of the tools, depending on their skills, as in the feature evaluation phase. The models were used to showcase the different tools, and evaluate their usability from the point of view of the 9 industry experts. A usability assessment in which the experts would directly interact with the tools was not considered reasonable, due to the skills required to master the tools, and to time constraints. Therefore, the three assessors showed the different characteristics of the tools in a 3-hours meeting with the experts, using the developed models as a reference. The experts were already familiar with the sample system considered, i.e., the moving-block system, which was also used as reference by other works [17]. The assessors asked the experts to evaluate the usability of each tool based on their first impression. It should be noticed that, although unorthodox, this approach is meaningful. In practical cases, formal tool users need to be tool experts [19], [42], and railway engineers will have to interact with them. This requires the engineers to be able to understand the models and make sense of the results, but not to be proficient with the formal tools.

The meeting was performed as follows:

- 1) **Introduction:** an introduction was given to recall the main principles of the considered system. This served to provide all participants a uniform perspective on the system that they were going to see modelled.

- 2) **Tool Showcase:** each tool was presented by an assessor in a 15 minutes presentation, covering the following aspects: 1. *General structure of the tool:* the presenter opens the tool, and provides a description of the graphical user interface (if available); 2. *Elements of the model:* the presenter opens the model, describes its architecture, and navigates it; 3. *Elements of the language:* minimal description of the modelling language constructs, based on the model shown; 4. *Simulation features:* a guided simulation is performed (if supported); 5. *Verification features:* description of the language used for formal verification, and presentation of a formal verification session with counter-example (if supported).
- 3) **Usability Evaluation:** after the presentation of each tool, a usability questionnaire for the tool (see below) is filled by the experts.

To evaluate the usability of the tool, we use a widely adopted usability questionnaire, namely, the System Usability Scale (SUS), developed by Brooke [79]. This was preferred to other questionnaires such as QSUC, QUIS and USE (see, e.g., [80] for pointers), as the questions were considered appropriate for our context. Some questions from the original SUS needed to be tailored to for our evaluation. The adapted questionnaire is as follows:

- 1) I think that I would like to use this tool frequently.
- 2) I found the tool unnecessarily complex.
- 3) I thought the tool was easy to use.
- 4) I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this tool.
- 5) I found the various functions in this tool were well integrated.
- 6) I thought there was too much inconsistency in this tool.
- 7) I would imagine that most people with industrial railway background would learn to use this tool very quickly.
- 8) I imagine that the tool would be very cumbersome to use.
- 9) I imagine that I would feel very confident using the tool.
- 10) I imagine I would need to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this tool.

Answers are given in a 5-points Likert Scale, where 0 = Completely Disagree; 1 = Partially Disagree; 2 = Undecided; 3 = Partially Agree; 4 = Agree. To calculate the SUS score, we follow the guidelines of Brooke [79]. Overall, the SUS Score varies between 0 and 100, with the following interpretations for the scores, based on the work of Bangor et al. [81] 100 = Best Imaginable; 85 = Excellent; 73 = Good; 52 = OK; 39 = Poor; 25 = Worst Imaginable.

IV. EXECUTION AND RESULTS

A. RQ1. Feature Selection

The feature selection process led to the identification of 33 features, which have been hierarchically grouped into *functional*, *language expressiveness* and *quality* features, with 8 subcategories in total. Below, we report categories, subcategories, associated descriptions, and possible values with related evaluation criteria.

a) *Functional Features:* Functional aspects have been organised in two subcategories: development functionalities and verification functionalities.

Development Functionalities.

- *Specification, modelling:* specifies whether the model can be edited graphically (GRA) or in some textual representation (TEXT) inside the tool, or whether the model is just imported as a textual file (TEXTIM).
- *Code generation:* indicates if the tool supports automated code generation from specifications (YES, NO).
- *Documentation and report generation:* the tool supports automated generation of readable reports and documents (YES), or allow the user to produce diagrams or partial reports that can be in principle included in official documentation (PARTIAL), or does not generate any usable documentation (NO).
- *Requirements traceability:* indicates if it is possible to trace requirements to the artifacts produced with the tool (YES, NO).
- *Project management:* specifies if the tool supports the management of a project, and the GUI-based navigation of its conceptual components (YES, NO).

Verification Functionalities.

- *Simulation:* indicates whether a model is executable, so that simulation is possible. The simulation could be either graphical (GRA) or textual (TEX), a mix of the two (MIX), or absent (NO).
 - *Formal verification:* the type of formal verification supported can be linear time model checking (MC-L), branching time model checking (MC-B), observer-based model checking (MC-O), theorem proving (TP), refinement checking (RF).
 - *Scalability approach:* indicates the type of approach adopted to verify large scale models. Can be On-the-fly model checking (OTF): the state is generated on demand; Partial order reduction (POR): exploitation of symmetries in the state space; Parallel computation (PAR): parallel computation distributed on more hosts; Bounded Model Checking (BMC): state space exploration up to a certain depth; Symbolic Model Checking (SYM): compact state space representation; SAT-SMT Constraint Solving and Theorem Proving (SCT): avoid explicit reasoning on the state space; Statistical Model Checking (SMC): avoid state space generation using simulations and provide an approximate solution; Compositionality and Minimization (COM): divide the problem into smaller subproblems; No technique (NO).
 - *Model-based testing:* support for automatically derived testing scenarios (YES, NO).
- b) *Language expressiveness:* This group of features collects technical aspects related to the main modelling language made available by the tool.
- *Non-determinism:* evaluates non-determinism is expressible. In particular whether the language allows internal non-deterministic system evolution (INT), or external

choices associated to inputs or trigger-events allow the expression of non-determinism (EXT).

- *Concurrency*: evaluates if and how concurrency aspects can be modelled. The model can be constituted by a set of asynchronously interacting elements (ASYNCH), synchronous elements (SYNCH), or just one element (NO).
- *Temporal aspects*: considers if modelling language supports the notion of time (YES, NO).
- *Stochastic aspects*: evaluates if it is possible to model aspects related to randomness, as for example stochastic delays (YES, NO).
- *Modularity of the language*: evaluates how the architecture of the model can be structured in the form of different hierarchically linked modules. The cases are: the tool allows the user to model in a hierarchical way, and the partitioning of the model into modules (HIGH); the tool allows the partitioning of the model into modules, but without a notion of hierarchy (MEDIUM); modules are supported, but they have no way to interact, neither by messages nor by shared memory (LOW); modules not supported (NO).
- *Supported data structures*: the language supports numeric types, but no composite expressions (BASIC), or has complex expressions like sequences, sets, array values (COMPLEX).
- *Float support*: indicates if floating point numbers are basic data types (YES, NO).

c) *Quality Features*: Quality aspects are organised into six categories: tool flexibility, maturity, usability, company constraints, and domain-specific criteria.

Tool flexibility.

- *Backward compatibility*: indicates to which extent models developed with previous versions of the tool can be used in the current version. Cases are: the vendor guarantees that legacy versions of the models can be used in the current version of the tool, or the future availability of legacy versions of the tool (YES); the tool is open source, or the input language is stable and *de facto* standard, or there is evidence of interest in preserving backward compatibility (LIKELY); the tool is not open source and the provider does not show evidence regarding backward compatibility (even if the language is rather stable and a *de facto* standard) (MODERATE); source code is not available, input format is not stable, and no information is available from the vendor (UNCERTAIN).
- *Standard input format*: evaluates if the the input language is based on a language standardised by an international organization (STANDARD); the input language is open, public and documented (OPEN); the structure of the model specifications is easily accessible, but not publicly documented (PARTIAL); the internal structure of the model specification is hidden (NO).
- *Import from or export to other tools*: evaluates whether the tool provides several import/export functionalities

(HIGH); the tool has a standard format used by other tools, or exports to some other formats (MEDIUM); the tool does not have import/export functionalities (LOW).

- *Modularity of the tool*: evaluates if the tool includes different modules and packages. Values are: the tool is composed of many modules that can be loaded to address different phases of the development process (HIGH); the tool offers multiple functionalities, but not in the form of loadable modules (MEDIUM); the tool offers a limited number of functionalities in a monolithic environment (LOW).
- *Team support*: specifies support for collaborative model development (YES,NO).

Maturity.

- *Industrial diffusion*: the website of the tool reports multiple (HIGH), a few (MEDIUM), or no (LOW) cases of industrial usage;
- *Stage of development*: the tool is a stable product with a long history of versions (MATURE); the tool is recent but with a solid infrastructure (PARTIAL); the tool is a prototype (PROTOTYPE).

Usability—in the broad sense of ISO 9241-11:2018 [82].

- *Availability of customer support*: considers if reliable customer support can be purchased for maintenance and training (YES); free support is available in the form of bug reports and forums (PARTIAL); or communications channels need to be established between producers and users to have support (NO).
- *Graphical user interface*: the tool has a well designed and powerful GUI (YES); a user friendly GUI exists, but it does not cover all the tool functionalities in a graphical form (PARTIAL); a GUI exists, but not particularly powerful (LIMITED); the tool is a command line one (NO).
- *Mathematical Background*: this feature aims at giving an idea of how easy is to learn the tool for an electronic or computer engineer (i.e., the typical railway practitioner). Cases are: the tool does not require particular logical/mathematical skills (BASIC); the tool requires the knowledge of temporal logic (MEDIUM); the tool requires the knowledge of theorem proving or process algebras (ADVANCED).
- *Quality of documentation*: the documentation is extensive, updated and clear, includes examples that can be used by domain experts, it is accessible and navigable in an easy way (EXCELLENT); the documentation is complete but offline, and requires some effort to be navigated (GOOD); the documentation is not sufficient, or not easily accessible (LIMITED).

Company constraints.

- *Cost*: the tool is available under payment only (PAY); free under certain conditions (e.g., academic) and moderate cost for industrial use (MIX); the tool is free (FREE).
- *Supported platforms*: indicates possible platforms supported by the tool (e.g., Windows, MacOS, Linux).

- *Complexity of license management*: the tool is free for commercial use, and no license management system is required (EASY); the tool offers academic and commercial licenses, both upon payment, limited effort was required to handle the academic license, and adequate information is provided for the commercial one (ADEQUATE); the tool has a free and a purchasable version, limited problems were encountered when trying the free version, but limited information is provided in the website about the licensing system of the other one (MODERATE); several problems were encountered with the license management system (COMPLEX).
- *Easy to install*: the tool requires little or no dependencies to external components (YES); the tool installation depends on non trivial external components, or the installation process is not smooth (PARTIAL); the installation process can interfere with the customer development environment (NO).

Domain-specific criteria.

- *CENELEC Certification*: the tool is certified according to the CENELEC norm (YES); the tool includes a CENELEC certification kit, or is certified according to other safety-related norms like DO178C [83] (PARTIAL); none of the above (NO).
- *Integration into the CENELEC process*: estimates how easy it is to integrate the tool in the existing railway life-cycle as described by CENELEC norms. Cases are: in the literature review from [11] or in the tool documentation was found evidence of tool usage for the development of railway products according to the CENELEC norms (YES); evidence was found of the usage of the tool in railways, but no CENELEC products developed with the support of the tool was found (MEDIUM); no evidence of usage of the tool in railways (LOW).

B. RQ2. Feature Evaluation

Fig. 1 reports the table resulting from the feature evaluation activity. The reader is invited to consult the sheet of each tool to have clarifications on the judgments provided. Here we summarise most evident trends, and contrast them with existing literature on desired features of formal tools in railway as indicated by recent surveys [11], [45], [46], and limitations and barriers for formal methods adoption (cf. [10], [15], [16], [18], [19], [84]–[86]).

Development Functionalities. Concerning development functionalities, we observe that the majority of the tools are based on textual specifications of the models (TEXT and TEXTIM), and, with the exception of Simulink and SCADE, most of them support only a limited subset of the other complementary functionalities, such as code generation and requirements traceability. Interestingly, the project management feature, which is common in any IDE for software development, is only available in four tools (Simulink, ProB, Atelier B, SCADE).

Observations. The tools appear to give limited relevance to development functionalities. This, to our knowledge, was

not observed by other authors discussing limitations of formal tools (cf. [10], [15], [16], [19]). Traceability in particular is regarded as one of the most relevant functionalities by railway stakeholders [11], who need to ensure that all the artifacts of the process are explicitly linked. The scarce support for traceability is therefore a relevant pain point. Concerning the type of specification language supported (graphical vs textual), some railway stakeholders may in principle prefer graphical languages [22], while few tools support them. However, Ottensooser et al. [87] have empirically shown that a pictorial specification is not necessarily more understandable than a textual one, and code-like models may be easier to maintain. Therefore, the need for graphical languages—and the understanding of specifications by all stakeholders—could be conflicting with the need for flexibility. Regardless of the type of language, a project management feature is needed to manage complex models.

Verification Functionalities. Verification functionalities, including model-based testing and simulation, are supported by a larger number of tools. However, specific strategies in terms of formal verification and scalability approaches are adopted by each platform, and this suggests a rather wide difference in terms of types of properties that can be verified on the models by each tool.

Observations. The difference between approaches is justified by the academic origin of most of the tools, which were primarily used to implement novel verification techniques, as observed by Garavel and Matescu [10]. This has an impact on the degree of experience required to master a tool. Several authors (cf. [10], [19], [42]) highlighted that the differences in terms of verification strategies, together with the wide range of optimization options made available to address scalability issues, require users to be experts in the tool to successfully verify large designs. The presence of several tools supporting model-based testing suggest that tool developers appear to be aware of the need for *complementarity* between testing and formal verification, which are not interchangeable activities.

Language Expressiveness. In terms of language expressiveness, the variety of feature value combinations, and therefore the specificity of each modelling language, is also quite evident, as for verification functionalities. In other terms, each tool is somewhat *unique*, both in terms of specification and in terms of verification strategies. Probabilistic aspects and floats have in general limited support. Only UPPAAL and mCLR2 allow the expression of probability, and floats are native types only for Simulink, nuXmv, UPPAAL, and SCADE.

Observations. The uniqueness of each language shows that after twenty years, the issues of *isolation* of formal specification languages pointed out by Lamsweerde [86] are still not solved. The limited support for floats suggests that, in most of the cases, tools are oriented to designing models that do not go down to the expressiveness of source code in terms of numerical data representation. Abstracting from details is nevertheless one of the principles of systems modelling, and other tools oriented to static analysis should be used to deal with errors arising from floating point numerical types [88].

Category	Name	SPIN	Simulink	nuXmv	ProB	AtelierB	UPPAAL	SCADE	FDR4	CPN T.	CADP	mCRL2	SAL	TLA+	UMC
Development Functionalities	Specification/Modeling	TEXT	GRA	TEXTIM	TEXT	TEXT	GRA	GRA	TEXTIN	GRA	TEXTIM	TEXT	TEXTIM	TEXT	TEXT
	Code Generation	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Document / Report Generation	PARTIAL	YES	NO	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	YES	PARTIAL	NO	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	NO	NO	PARTIAL
	Requirements Traceability	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Project Management	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Verification Functionalities	Simulation	TEX	GRA	TEX	MIX	NO	GRA	GRA	TEX	GRA	TEX	TEX	TEX	NO	TEX
	Scalability approach	OTF, POR, PAR	BMC	BMC, SYM	SCT	SCT	SMC, SYM	BMC	COM, POR	BMC	COM, PAR	COM	PAR, SCT	SYM, SCT	OTF
	Formal Verification	MC-L	MC-O	MC-L, MC-B	MC-L, MC-B, RF	TP	MC-L, RF	MC-O	RF	MC-B	MC-B, RF	MC-B, RF	MC-L, TP	MC-L, TP	MC-B
	Model-based Testing	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
Language Expressiveness	Nondeterminism	INT	EXT	INT, EXT	INT, EXT	INT, EXT	INT, EXT	EXT	INT, EXT	INT	INT, EXT	INT, EXT	INT, EXT	INT	INT
	Concurrency	ASYNCH	NO	SYNCH	NO	NO	SYNCH	SYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH, SYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH, SYNCH
	Temporal Aspects	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
	Probabilistic or Stochastic Aspects	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
	Modularity of the Language	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	HIGH
	Supported Data Structures	BASIC	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX
	Float Support	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Tool Flexibility	Backward Compatibility	LIKELY	LIKELY	LIKELY	LIKELY	MODERATE	LIKELY	LIKELY	MODERATE	LIKELY	LIKELY	LIKELY	MODERATE	MODERATE	MODERATE
	Standard Input Format	OPEN	PARTIAL	OPEN	OPEN	OPEN	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	OPEN	PARTIAL	STANDARD	OPEN	OPEN	OPEN	STANDARD
	Import/Export	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM
	Modularity of the Tool	LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
	Team Support	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Maturity	Industrial Diffusion	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW
	Stage of Development	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	PROTO.
Usability	Customer Support	PARTIAL	YES	PARTIAL	YES	YES	YES	YES	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL
	Graphical User Interface	LIMITED	YES	NO	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	YES	YES	LIMITED	PARTIAL	LIMITED	PARTIAL	NO	LIMITED	PARTIAL
	Mathematical Background	MEDIUM	BASIC	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	ADVANCED	MEDIUM	BASIC	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	ADVANCED	ADVANCED	ADVANCED	ADVANCED	MEDIUM
	Quality of Documentation	GOOD	EXCELLENT	GOOD	GOOD	EXCELLENT	GOOD	EXCELLENT	EXCELLENT	GOOD	GOOD	GOOD	GOOD	GOOD	LIMITED
Company Constraints	Cost	FREE	PAY	MIX	FREE	FREE	MIX	PAY	MIX	FREE	MIX	FREE	FREE	FREE	FREE
	Supported Platforms	Windows, Linux,	Windows	Windows, Linux,	Windows	Windows, Linux,									
	Complexity of License Management	EASY	ADEQUATE	EASY	EASY	EASY	MODERATE	ADEQUATE	MODERATE	EASY	MODERATE	EASY	EASY	EASY	EASY
	Easy to Install	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	PARTIAL	YES	YES	YES	YES
Railway-specific Criteria	CENELEC Certification	NO	PARTIAL	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Integration into the CENELEC Process	MEDIUM	YES	MEDIUM	YES	YES	MEDIUM	YES	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM

Fig. 1: Evaluation Table

We note that probabilistic features are traditionally associated to specialised tools for the analysis of performances and other dependability aspects [12], [13]. In this paper we consider tools oriented towards system design, and this is the reason why this feature has limited support.

Tool Flexibility. Tool flexibility sees a major weakness in the team support feature, with Atelier B as the only tool including it. Only Simulink, ProB, UPPAAL, SCADE and CADP can be regarded as flexible toolboxes (cf. “Modularity of the Tool” = HIGH), and only ProB, CADP and mCLR2 are open to different formats with several import/export functionalities. This suggests that in many cases the tools are independent ecosystems, and their integrated usage may be complicated.

Observations. This issue also observed by other authors [10], [19], who pointed out the high degree of specialisation of languages and tools. Combining at least a subset of the tools and integrating them in a coherent process is extremely

relevant. Indeed, as observed by previous work [17], [89], the needs of an industrial process cannot be fulfilled by one formal tool only.

Maturity. The majority of the tools has a mature stage of development, and diffusion appears to be medium-high.

Observations. The high degree of industry-readiness observed is in contrast with the observation of previous work (see, e.g., [8], [85]) reporting that the low maturity and prototypical level of many tools are among the main obstacles for formal methods adoption. As maturity is, by far, recognised as the most relevant quality attribute that a formal tool should have to be applied in the conservative world of railways [45], [46], we argue that low maturity can be considered as a false barrier for formal methods adoption.

Usability. Usability aspects appear, at first glance, as major pain points, with limited customer support, limited GUI and the need for a medium to advanced mathematical background.

Observations. Ease of learning, which is the second most desired feature [45], [46], is notoriously a problem for formal tools [15], [90], which is complicated by the decreasing mathematical competence of engineers over the years [90]. In this sense our work confirms the literature. On the other hand, it also highlights that, to address this problem, not only engineering curricula should be enriched, and better GUIs should be developed, but also more effort should be dedicated to customer support, which is acceptable only for Simulink, ProB, Atelier B, SCADE and UPPAAL.

Company Constraints. Company constraints are in general fulfilled, with several platforms supported and ease of install and license management. This confirms the maturity and industry-readiness of the majority of the tools—see “Maturity” for related observations.

Railway-specific Criteria. Railway specific criteria are not fulfilled, with MEDIUM-LOW easiness in integrating a tool in the CENELEC process, and only one tool, namely SCADE, being certified. However, four tools, namely Atelier B, ProB, SCADE and Simulink have been used to develop railway products, indicating that their integration in the CENELEC process is at least possible.

Observations. The issue of CENELEC integration is regarded as the third most desired quality feature by railway practitioners [45], [46]. It appears that a major pain point that industry may face is that practitioners do not have guidance to accommodate these tools within their industrial processes, and how to combine the tools together in a flexible way. This was also observed in other domains, such as aerospace [15].

C. RQ3. Usability Evaluation

Fig. 2 presents the results of the SUS questionnaire. The tools that were considered most usable are Simulink (SUS Score = 76.38) and SCADE (69.16). These are formal model-based development tools, with appealing, effective GUIs, powerful languages and simulation capabilities. The two tools are followed by three other tools with acceptable GUIs, but with widely different capabilities, namely ProB (SUS Score = 62.2), UPPAAL (61.7) and UMC (57.2). ProB and UMC allow the user to model in textual form, but presents the results of the simulation also in graphical form. Instead, the UPPAAL language is entirely graphical, and presents a graphical simulation style that recalls the message sequence charts, which are well known by railway practitioners. SPIN (SUS Score = 56.9), Atelier B (45.5) and nuXmv (36.6), with some differences, are considered among the least usable tools. Although SPIN is a command line tool, without a GUI, its scores are higher than Atelier B. This can be explained considering the following observations discussed with the participants: (a) SPIN uses a modelling language that is very similar to the C language, and therefore was considered familiar by the participants, who, in turn, gave higher scores; (b) Atelier B uses a refinement-based theorem proving approach, which requires advanced skills to be mastered. When computing the *average* SUS Score, we obtain 58.22, which is between OK and Good [81]. Hence, the general usability of the tools can be considered acceptable.

Fig. 2: SUS for the different tools.

V. SUMMARY AND IMPLICATIONS

Within the inherent limitations of the DESMET methodology [44], our main take-away messages: 1) formal tools lack support for development features and process-integration aspects; 2) most of the tools are independent ecosystems, with unique, non-standard languages and specialised verification capabilities; 3) formal tools are mature, as highly desired by railway industry [45], [46]; 4) most usability aspects appear to be low in principle, but, when tools are assessed by practitioners, usability is considered acceptable.

In the following, we discuss the main implications of our results. Our goal is to foster the debate about the adoption of formal tools in safety-critical software engineering, and therefore we also indulge in giving personal opinions.

Implications for Tool Developers. The majority of the considered formal tools lack support for process-related aspects, including development functionalities such as traceability and document/report generation, and no evidence of their integration in the railway process. With some differences, exceptions are Simulink, SCADE, Atelier B and ProB. Tool developers are encouraged to give more relevance to process-related aspects and enrich their tools with additional development functionalities. Furthermore, they are encouraged to invest in customer support and consultancy: companies need to be accompanied in the introduction of novel tools, and tailored recommendations need to be provided on how to best adapt their processes. Making their tools more interoperable is also recommended.

Implications for Researchers. Tool certification, or qualification according to the norms, is regarded as a relevant problem by industrial practitioners, as also observed by Garavel [10] and Mazzanti [42]. However, only SCADE is CENELEC certified. Nevertheless, if a formal tool does not go down to code generation, as in most of the cases, we argue that tool qualification is not a radical issue. Railway systems get certified also without using formal design tools, as these are highly recommended but not *required* [16]. We argue that evidence should be provided in terms of *cost-benefit* analyses on the introduction of formal methods. Researchers should focus more on empirically showing that introducing a formal

tool actually allows companies to reduce the cost of the testing phase, either by detecting errors beforehand, or by facilitating the production of test cases.

Our work shows that the usability of the tools is in general *acceptable*. We also observe that there are conflicting reports regarding the ease of learning of tools that require advanced mathematical background. For example, Newcombe et al. [91] reported that Amazon engineers with no prior knowledge of formal tools required only few weeks of training to utilize the tool, and similar reports are available for the B method [92]. Therefore, circumstantial evidence seems to contradict common beliefs about the inherent complexity of learning formal methods, and we encourage more empirically grounded evaluation to answer the question: “Are formal methods truly difficult?”.

Implications for Railway Practitioners. Several suggestions have been given to address the skill barriers, and are mostly oriented to improve education of engineers [15], [90]. However, we argue that this may be a workable problem. To be effectively used, formal tools require experts in formal methods and in the chosen tool itself [19], [42]. Engineers need to understand the principles of a tool to interact with the experts, but do not need to be able to use the tool. Our usability study suggests that current tools may be sufficiently acceptable by railway experts, when they see the tools used by another subject. Considering that also the maturity prejudice is not well-funded, we invite practitioners to overcome their skepticism [8], and give a chance to formal tools.

VI. THREATS TO VALIDITY

Construct Validity. The set of considered tools does not represent the complete universe of formal platforms. However, the tool selection rationale was motivated by other works in railways [17], and by the need to have representatives of different families (see Sect. III). Overall, there is a bias towards model checking tools with respect to theorem proving ones, but this also occurs in the railway literature, where the preference for this technique is rather common [5]. It is worth noting that we did not purchase commercial licenses for those product offering them. This should not affect our evaluation, as academic licenses appear to support the same features.

The different features, as well as the possible values, were defined by a limited group. However, the group represents academic and railway industry viewpoints, and several triangulation activities were carried out to ensure clarity, a sufficient degree of completeness, and a uniform interpretation.

The tool adopted to evaluate usability, i.e., the SUS questionnaire, is widely used and has been proven effective [81]. On the other hand, the presented usability evaluation is based on a showcase of the tools and different results may be obtained with a direct evaluation by railway experts.

Internal Validity. The evaluation of the tools may have suffered from subjectivity. To limit this problem, triangulation activities were performed to align the evaluation, and the assessors were required to report appropriate evidence in the evaluation sheet, when some judgment required explicit

justification. For some features, the value also depends on the available evidence that comes from the literature and from the websites of the tool, and may not reflect the reality. To mitigate these aspects, different sources of information, and practical tool trials have been considered.

In the usability study the researchers could have biased the audience towards a certain tool, based on their preferences. To mitigate this threat, before the evaluation the researchers rehearsed the tool showcase, with the participation of one of the academic experts, and provided mutual recommendations. Therefore, we argue that the tools were presented in a quite uniform manner. An exception is SCADE, which was presented through a video, instead of a live presentation, due to licensing rights. Another issue is related to the number of subjects involved, i.e., 9, which may be regarded as a limited sample. However, it has been shown that a group of 10 users can identify 80% of the usability problems [93]. Therefore, we argue that, although limited, the sample size is in line with the samples normally used in usability testing.

External Validity. The usability evaluation, as well as the preceding activities, involved railway experts with multiple roles, i.e., designers, developers, testers and managers, and with different degrees of experience in railways, although more than 10 years. This covers a large spectrum of perspectives. On the other hand, the participants were all from the same railway company, and this may limit the results. However, it is worth noticing that railway companies follow standardised processes, and, in addition, railway products are also well-established and even standardised in some cases (e.g., ERTMS [76]). Therefore, we argue that the perspectives of companies may be similar to each other, thus suggesting a sufficient degree of external validity of our results.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a systematic evaluation and a usability analysis of 14 formal tools for railway system design. We show that the majority of the tools are mature and consolidated products, with a sufficient degree of industry readiness. Although many tools have limited GUIs, and require strong mathematical background, our usability study shows that, in average, the degree of usability is between OK and Good, thus suggesting that usability may not be a strong barrier for formal tools’ adoption. Main limitations are the limited support for development functionalities, such as traceability, and other process-integration features. We share our evaluation sheets [47], which include synthetic yet industry-relevant information about each single tool.

Our work, and the shared data, can be useful to practitioners interested in introducing formal methods in their company, and to the research community of software engineers dealing with system development. Through our contribution, these different profiles can have a clear and up-to-date opinion about the landscape of available tools, and their salient characteristics. Tool developers can profit from our independent evaluation to identify the pain points of their platforms, and introduce improvements.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Chiappini, A. Cimatti, L. Macchi, O. Rebollo, M. Roveri, A. Susi, S. Tonetta, and B. Vittorini, "Formalization and Validation of a subset of the European Train Control System," in *ICSE*, vol. 2. ACM, 2010, pp. 109–118.
- [2] A. Ferrari, D. Grasso, G. Magnani, A. Fantechi, and M. Tempestini, "The Metrô Rio case study," *SCP*, vol. 78, no. 7, pp. 828–842, 2013.
- [3] A. E. Haxthausen, J. Peleska, and S. Kinder, "A formal approach for the construction and verification of railway control systems," *FAOC*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 191–219, 2011.
- [4] K. Winter and N. J. Robinson, "Modelling large railway interlockings and model checking small ones," in *ACSC 2003*, ser. CRPIT, vol. 16. Australian Computer Society, 2003, pp. 309–316.
- [5] A. Fantechi, "Twenty-Five Years of Formal Methods and Railways: What Next?" in *Revised Selected Papers of the SEFM*, ser. LNCS, vol. 8368. Germany: Springer, 2013, pp. 167–183.
- [6] A. Fantechi, A. Ferrari, and S. Gnesi, "Formal Methods and Safety Certification: Challenges in the Railways Domain," in *ISO/SA*, ser. LNCS, vol. 9953. Germany: Springer, 2016, pp. 261–265.
- [7] J. M. Wing, "A specifier's introduction to formal methods," *IEEE Computer*, vol. 23, no. 9, pp. 8–22, 1990.
- [8] J. Woodcock, P. G. Larsen, J. Bicarregui, and J. Fitzgerald, "Formal methods: Practice and experience," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 19:1–19:36, 2009.
- [9] H. Garavel and S. Graf, "Bsi study 875: Formal methods for safe and secure computer systems," Tech. Rep., 2013.
- [10] H. Garavel and R. Mateescu, "Reflections on bernhard steffen's physics of software tools," in *Models, Mindsets, Meta: The What, the How, and the Why Not?* Springer, 2019, pp. 186–207.
- [11] A. Ferrari, M. H. ter Beek, F. Mazzanti, D. Basile, A. Fantechi, S. Gnesi, A. Piattino, and D. Trentini, "Survey on Formal Methods and Tools in Railways: The ASTRail Approach," in *RSSRail*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11495. Springer, 2019, pp. 226–241.
- [12] A. Hartmanns and H. Hermanns, "In the quantitative automata zoo," *SCP*, vol. 112, pp. 3–23, 2015.
- [13] J.-P. Katoen, "The probabilistic model checking landscape," in *LICS*, 2016, pp. 31–45.
- [14] European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization, "CENELEC EN 50128— Railway applications – Communication, signalling and processing systems – Software for railway control and protection systems," 1 June 2011, <https://standards.globalspec.com/std/1678027/cenelec-en-50128>.
- [15] J. A. Davis, M. Clark, D. Cofer, A. Ficarek, J. Hinchman, J. Hoffman, B. Hulbert, S. P. Miller, and L. Wagner, "Study on the barriers to the industrial adoption of formal methods," in *FMICS*. Springer, 2013, pp. 63–77.
- [16] M. Nyberg, D. Gurov, C. Lidström, A. Rasmusson, and J. Westman, "Formal verification in automotive industry: Enablers and obstacles," in *ISOLA*. Springer, 2018, pp. 139–158.
- [17] A. Ferrari, F. Mazzanti, D. Basile, M. H. ter Beek, and A. Fantechi, "Comparing Formal Tools for System Design: a Judgment Study," in *ICSE*. ACM, 2020, pp. 62–74.
- [18] R. Schlick, M. Felderer, I. Majzik, R. Nardone, A. Raschke, C. Snook, and V. Vittorini, "A proposal of an example and experiments repository to foster industrial adoption of formal methods," in *ISOLA*. Springer, 2018, pp. 249–272.
- [19] B. Steffen, "The physics of software tools: Swot analysis and vision," *JSTTT*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2017.
- [20] J.-R. Abrial, "Formal Methods: Theory Becoming Practice," *JUCS*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 619–628, 2007.
- [21] M. Leuschel, J. Falampin, F. Fritz, and D. Plagge, "Automated property verification for large scale B models with ProB," *FAOC*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 683–709, 2011.
- [22] A. Ferrari, A. Fantechi, S. Gnesi, and G. Magnani, "Model-based development and formal methods in the railway industry," *IEEE software*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 28–34, 2013.
- [23] F. Moller, H. N. Nguyen, M. Roggenbach, S. Schneider, and H. Treharne, "Defining and Model Checking Abstractions of Complex Railway Models Using CSP||B," in *HVC 2012*, ser. LNCS, vol. 7857. Springer, 2013, pp. 193–208.
- [24] M. Ghazel, "Formalizing a subset of ERTMS/ETCS specifications for verification purposes," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 42, pp. 60–75, 2014.
- [25] P. James, F. Moller, H. N. Nguyen, M. Roggenbach, S. Schneider, and H. Treharne, "Techniques for modelling and verifying railway interlockings," *JSTTT*, vol. 16, pp. 685–711, 2014.
- [26] M. Bosschaert, E. Quaglietta, B. Janssen, and R. M. P. Goverde, "Efficient formalization of railway interlocking data in RailML," *Information Systems*, vol. 49, pp. 126–141, 2015.
- [27] R. Nardone, U. Gentile, M. Benerecetti, A. Peron, V. Vittorini, S. Marrone, and N. Mazzocca, "Modeling Railway Control Systems in Promela," in *FTSCS 2015*, vol. 596. Germany: Springer, 2016, pp. 121–136.
- [28] D. Basile, F. Di Giandomenico, and S. Gnesi, "Statistical Model Checking of an Energy-Saving Cyber-Physical System in the Railway Domain," in *SAC 2017*. ACM, 2017, pp. 1356–1363.
- [29] T. Lecomte, D. Déharbe, É. Prun, and E. Mottin, "Applying a Formal Method in Industry: A 25-Year Trajectory," in *SBMF 2017*, ser. LNCS, vol. 10623. Springer, 2017, pp. 70–87.
- [30] L. H. Vu, A. E. Haxthausen, and J. Peleska, "Formal modelling and verification of interlocking systems featuring sequential release," *SCP*, vol. 133, pp. 91–115, 2017.
- [31] P. Arcaini, P. Ježek, and J. Kofroň, "Modelling the Hybrid ERTM-SETCS Level 3 Case Study in Spin," in *ABZ 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 10817. Germany: Springer, 2018, pp. 277–291.
- [32] M. Bartholomeus, B. Luttik, and T. Willemse, "Modeling and Analysing ERTMS Hybrid Level 3 with the mCRL2 Toolset," in *FMICS 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11119. Springer, 2018, pp. 98–114.
- [33] D. Basile, M. H. ter Beek, and V. Ciancia, "Statistical Model Checking of a Moving Block Railway Signalling Scenario with UPPAAL SMC," in *ISO/SA 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11245. Springer, 2018, pp. 372–391.
- [34] M. H. ter Beek, S. Gnesi, and A. Knapp, "Formal methods for transport systems," *JSTTT*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 237–241, 2018.
- [35] U. Berger, P. James, A. Lawrence, M. Roggenbach, and M. Seisenberger, "Verification of the European Rail Traffic Management System in Real-Time Maude," *SCP*, vol. 154, pp. 61–88, 2018.
- [36] A. Cunha and N. Macedo, "Validating the Hybrid ERTMS/ETCS Level 3 Concept with Electrum," in *ABZ 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 10817. Springer, 2018, pp. 307–321.
- [37] A. Iliassov, D. Taylor, L. Laibinis, and A. B. Romanovsky, "Formal Verification of Signalling Programs with SafeCap," in *SAFECOMP 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11093. Springer, 2018, pp. 91–106.
- [38] A. Mammar, M. Frappier, S. J. Tuono Fotso, and R. Laleau, "An Event-B Model of the Hybrid ERTMS/ETCS Level 3 Standard," in *ABZ 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 10817. Germany: Springer, 2018, pp. 353–366.
- [39] F. Mazzanti and A. Ferrari, "Ten Diverse Formal Models for a CBTC Automatic Train Supervision System," in *MARS/VPT*, ser. Electronic Proceedings in Theoretical Computer Science, vol. 268, 2018, pp. 104–149.
- [40] S. Vanit-Anunchai, "Modelling and simulating a Thai railway signalling system using Coloured Petri Nets," *JSTTT*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 243–262, 2018.
- [41] D. Basile, M. H. ter Beek, A. Ferrari, and A. Legay, "Modelling and Analysing ERTMS L3 Moving Block Railway Signalling with Simulink and UPPAAL SMC," in *FMICS 2019*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11687. Springer, 2019.
- [42] F. Mazzanti, A. Ferrari, and G. O. Spagnolo, "Towards formal methods diversity in railways: an experience report with seven frameworks," *JSTTT*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 263–288, 2018.
- [43] A. E. Haxthausen, H. N. Nguyen, and M. Roggenbach, "Comparing formal verification approaches of interlocking systems," in *RSSRail*, ser. LNCS, vol. 9707. Springer, 2016, pp. 160–177.
- [44] B. Kitchenham, S. Linkman, and D. Law, "DESMET: a methodology for evaluating software engineering methods and tools," *Computing & Control Engineering Journal*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 120–126, 1997.
- [45] D. Basile, M. H. ter Beek, A. Fantechi, S. Gnesi, F. Mazzanti, A. Piattino, D. Trentini, and A. Ferrari, "On the Industrial Uptake of Formal Methods in the Railway Domain— A Survey with Stakeholders," in *IFM 2018*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11023. Germany: Springer, 2018, pp. 20–29.
- [46] M. H. ter Beek, A. Borälv, A. Fantechi, A. Ferrari, S. Gnesi, C. Löfving, and F. Mazzanti, "Adopting Formal Methods in an Industrial Setting: The Railways Case," in *FM*, ser. LNCS, vol. 11800. Springer, 2019, pp. 762–772.
- [47] [Online]. Available: 10.5281/zenodo.4005286
- [48] Y. Bertot and P. Castéran, *Interactive Theorem Proving and Program Development - Coq'Art: The Calculus of Inductive Constructions*, ser.

- Texts in Theoretical Computer Science. An EATCS Series. Springer, 2004.
- [49] W. Bibel, *Automated theorem proving*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [50] M. Fitting, *First-order logic and automated theorem proving*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [51] E. M. Clarke, O. Grumberg, and D. A. Peled, *Model Checking*. MIT Press, 1999.
- [52] C. Baier and J.-P. Katoen, *Principles of Model Checking*. MIT Press, 2008.
- [53] E. M. Clarke, T. A. Henzinger, H. Veith, and R. Bloem, Eds., *Handbook of Model Checking*. Springer, 2018.
- [54] T. Gibson-Robinson, P. J. Armstrong, A. Boulgakov, and A. W. Roscoe, “FDR3: a parallel refinement checker for CSP,” vol. 18, no. 2, 2016, pp. 149–167.
- [55] M. H. Sørensen and P. Urzyczyn, *Lectures on the Curry-Howard Isomorphism*, ser. Studies in Logic and the Foundations of Mathematics. USA: Elsevier Science Inc., 2006, vol. 149.
- [56] ClearSy, *AtelierB Training Manual*, 2002.
- [57] L. C. Paulson, *Isabelle: A generic theorem prover*. Springer Science & Business Media, 1994, vol. 828.
- [58] G. J. Holzmann, *The SPIN model checker: Primer and reference manual*. Addison-Wesley Reading, 2004, vol. 1003.
- [59] M. H. ter Beek, A. Fantechi, S. Gnesi, and F. Mazzanti, “A state/event-based model-checking approach for the analysis of abstract system properties,” *SCP*, vol. 76, no. 2, pp. 119 – 135, 2011, selected papers from FMICS.
- [60] A. Biere, A. Cimatti, E. M. Clarke, M. Fujita, and Y. Zhu, “Symbolic model checking using sat procedures instead of bdds,” in *DAC*. IEEE, 1999, pp. 317–320.
- [61] A. Cimatti, E. M. Clarke, F. Giunchiglia, and M. Roveri, “Nusmv: A new symbolic model verifier,” in *CAV*, ser. CAV ’99. Springer-Verlag, 1999, p. 495–499.
- [62] A. Legay, B. Delahaye, and S. Bensalem, “Statistical Model Checking: An overview,” in *RV 2010*, ser. LNCS, vol. 6418. Springer, 2010, pp. 122–135.
- [63] A. David, K. G. Larsen, A. Legay, M. Mikucionis, and D. B. Poulsen, “Uppaal smc tutorial,” *JSTTT*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 397–415, Aug 2015.
- [64] L. Lamport, *Specifying Systems: The TLA+ Language and Tools for Hardware and Software Engineers*. Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., 2002.
- [65] L. de Moura, S. Owre, H. Rueß, J. Rushby, N. Shankar, M. Sorea, and A. Tiwari, “Sal 2,” in *CAV*, R. Alur and D. A. Peled, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2004, pp. 496–500.
- [66] J. B. Dabney and T. L. Harman, *Mastering simulink*. Pearson, 2004.
- [67] G. Berry, “Scade: Synchronous design and validation of embedded control software,” in *Next Generation Design and Verification Methodologies for Distributed Embedded Control Systems*, S. Ramesh and P. Sampath, Eds. Springer Netherlands, 2007, pp. 19–33.
- [68] P. Fritzon and V. Engelson, “Modelica—a unified object-oriented language for system modeling and simulation,” in *European Conference on Object-Oriented Programming*. Springer, 1998, pp. 67–90.
- [69] E. Bartocci, D. Beyer, P. E. Black, G. Fedyukovich, H. Garavel, A. Hartmanns, M. Huisman, F. Kordon, J. Nagele, M. Sighireanu *et al.*, “Toolympics 2019: An overview of competitions in formal methods,” in *TACAS*. Springer, 2019, pp. 3–24.
- [70] M. Jasper, M. Mues, A. Murtovi, M. Schlüter, F. Howar, B. Steffen, M. Schordan, D. Hendriks, R. Schiffelers, H. Kuppens *et al.*, “Rers 2019: Combining synthesis with real-world models,” in *TACAS*. Springer, 2019, pp. 101–115.
- [71] B. Steffen, T. Margaria, and V. Braun, “The electronic tool integration platform: concepts and design,” *JSTTT*, vol. 1, no. 1-2, pp. 9–30, 1997.
- [72] D. Bjørner, “New Results and Trends in Formal Techniques and Tools for the Development of Software for Transportation Systems— A Review,” in *FORMS 2003*. Hungary: L’Harmattan, 2003.
- [73] A. Fantechi, W. Fokkink, and A. Morzenti, “Some Trends in Formal Methods Applications to Railway Signaling,” in *FMICS: A Survey of Applications*. John Wiley & Sons, 2013, ch. 4, pp. 61–84.
- [74] *Railway Safety, Reliability, and Security: Technologies and Systems Engineering*. USA: IGI Global, 2012.
- [75] *Formal Methods Applied to Industrial Complex Systems— Implementation of the B Method*. USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [76] T. S. Hoang, M. Butler, and K. Reichl, “The hybrid ertms/ets level 3 case study,” in *ABZ*. Springer, 2018, pp. 251–261.
- [77] C. Newcombe, “Why amazon chose tla+,” in *ABZ*. Springer, 2014, pp. 25–39.
- [78] R. Scupin, “The KJ Method: A Technique for Analyzing Data Derived from Japanese Ethnology,” *Hum. Organ.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 233–237, 1997.
- [79] J. Brooke, “Sus: a “quick and dirty” usability,” *Usability evaluation in industry*, p. 189, 1996.
- [80] P. Pourali and J. M. Atlee, “An empirical investigation to understand the difficulties and challenges of software modellers when using modelling tools,” in *MODELS*, 2018, pp. 224–234.
- [81] A. Bangor, P. T. Kortum, and J. T. Miller, “An empirical evaluation of the system usability scale,” *IJHCI*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 574–594, 2008.
- [82] ISO/TC 159/SC 4, “ISO 9241-11:2018. Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts,” 2019.
- [83] L. Rierson, *Developing safety-critical software: a practical guide for aviation software and DO-178C compliance*. CRC Press, 2017.
- [84] Y. A. Ameur, F. Boniol, and V. Wiels, “Toward a wider use of formal methods for aerospace systems design and verification,” *JSTTT*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2010.
- [85] J. M. Atlee, S. Beidu, N. A. Day, F. Faghieh, and P. Shaker, “Recommendations for improving the usability of formal methods for product lines,” in *FormaliSE*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 43–49.
- [86] A. v. Lamsweerde, “Formal specification: a roadmap,” in *FOSE*, 2000, pp. 147–159.
- [87] A. Ottensooser, A. Fekete, H. A. Reijers, J. Mendling, and C. Menicetas, “Making sense of business process descriptions: An experimental comparison of graphical and textual notations,” *JSS*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 596–606, 2012.
- [88] M. Moscato, L. Titolo, A. Dutle, and C. A. Munoz, “Automatic estimation of verified floating-point round-off errors via static analysis,” in *SAFECOMP*. Springer, 2017, pp. 213–229.
- [89] M. Gleirscher, S. Foster, and J. Woodcock, “New opportunities for integrated formal methods,” *CSUR*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 1–36, 2019.
- [90] D. Bjørner and K. Havelund, “40 years of formal methods,” in *FM*. Springer, 2014, pp. 42–61.
- [91] C. Newcombe, T. Rath, F. Zhang, B. Munteanu, M. Brooker, and M. Deardeuff, “How amazon web services uses formal methods,” *CACM*, vol. 58, no. 4, p. 66–73, 2015.
- [92] A. G. Russo, “Formal methods as an improvement tool,” in *Industrial Deployment of System Engineering Methods*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 81–95.
- [93] W. Hwang and G. Salvendy, “Number of people required for usability evaluation: the 10±2 rule,” *CACM*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 130–133, 2010.